

International Journal for Research in Science Engineering & Technology (IJRSET)

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15294716>

MONITORING AND ANALYZING POWER PLANT VARIABLES PERFORMANCE, CASE STUDY OF OLKARIA

¹ John G. Deng, ² Dr. Edwell Tafara Mharakurwa, ³ Dr. P. Waweru Njeri

¹Department of Geothermal Training and Research Institute, ^{2,3}Department of Electrical & electronics engineering, ^{1,2,3}Dedan Kimathi University of Technology, ^{1,2,3}Nyeri Kenya.

ABSTRACT: Power control system variables are very important in the power plant, generation, and distribution and also play a great role in modern life. Besides that, voltage, frequency and current have the very essential impact on the modernization, economic, political, and social aspects in every country and the whole world. The power variables (current, voltage & Frequency) need stable mode, control, and protection of home appliances, and human life, and also reduce the cost of electricity bills by deploying the best technology. New technologies in power systems are well-equipped with several protection schemes. This study aims at minimizing the unpredicted events and power outages, and incorrect operating conditions in the power control systems. If the applications comprising power systems are not well controlled, the power system is likely to result in power system failures that might lead to a blackout. Because of this case, many researchers in Kenya and around the whole world have researched how to avoid temporary failures in power control systems. In this study, a lot of results and assessments expected have been carried out on the power outages, blackouts, and unknown events that occur in the systems that were identified and

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the unreliability of electricity has increased due to technology challenges, limited transmission paths, security improvement, efficiency concerns, renewable energy generation (geothermal, wind, solar, and hydropower energy) integration, emission reductions, and varying types of other distributed generation resources. These complex variables especially the voltage and current require better monitoring and system awareness of the electric power grid. The use of Synchrophasor provides the ability to measure phase angles with absolute time references, and this characteristic presents a potential solution for improving system monitoring and awareness. Through many types of research that have been carried out on the power plant's variable so far, the power imbalance between demand and generation directly affect the

monitored. The characteristics of voltage, current, frequency fluctuation, and other parameters in power systems and select favourable technology that was used during power operation and on-site in the geothermal field. Therefore, this research has come up with a new mechanism for addressing these problems by using Synchrophasor technology data implemented in Simulink MATLAB Simulink Software. This technology was used in the power system and in the field to monitor power and prevent daily power blackouts. Moreover, the challenges in the existing protective schemes and research gaps in the topic of power system blackouts and cascading events were marked. This study was addressed by using Synchrophasor technology (PMU Connection Tester software) and Matlab Simulink software. The results from this case study were used to analyze and solve the existing problem. Research methodology and issues to be considered in future power system blackout studies are also proposed.

Keywords: [Power system, Simulink MATLAB, Synchrophasor technology, Power Variables.]

frequency stability, while the voltage is directly affected by the reactive power imbalance as one of the root cause of this problem.

In situations where these abnormal conditions are not addressed in time, the system would experience cascading events that might lead to a blackout.

Measurement and monitoring of electrical quantities (voltage, current, frequency etc.) hold high significance as it reflects the operating state of the power system. Any deviation in these quantities is indicative of an event that might disrupt the normal functioning of the system. With the ever-growing demand for energy and the focus to maintain the reliability of the system, monitoring and measurement of electrical quantities have occupied front-end positions. Today, the focus of power engineers is on creating a smart grid that can bring efficiency and sustainability in the fast-growing demand scenario in addition to facilitating the bi-directional flow of

sections that include monitoring, transmission line and generation part. In this model, a fault detector parameter was deployed to identify the errors and faults and this is what makes this bus power system model unique.

Figure -2 10 bus power system model

Voltage Measurement

The voltage was measured using Simulink and the results obtained from this experiment came as expected from 415 volts. This is in alignment with Kenya’s three-phase standard. The main purpose of this graph was to demonstrate the voltage measurement and monitoring during simulation. We use a standard bus power system with a bit of modification to meet the study objectives and scope. This study also deploys fault detector parameters to deter the errors and faults in voltage, current and frequency during simulation. The purpose of these results is to know the exact voltage digit and current. The results address the objectives of monitoring, and determining the quality and quantity of power and also address the objectives of stabilizing voltage, current and frequency in the power system.

The fault was detected in load 3

The Fault detector parameter was connected to detect errors and faults in the voltage, and current during simulation. This was in response to reducing the errors and stabilising the power variables (current, frequency and Voltage) in the power system using Simulink MATLAB integrated with the Phasor Measurement Units (PMU) Parameter. This result addresses the objective that talks about identifying and reducing errors in this study.

This was detected during voltage measurement which had run for 0.1 seconds. The fault detected was a short circuit caused by an unconnected line in load 3.

Voltage fault detection system using simulink MATLAB

This figure demonstrates the importance of deploying fault detector parameters in the bus power system model. After the correction of errors and faults at load The result shows zero errors and faults in the bus power system model and load 3 in particular.

Frequency measurement in PMU section on SIMULINKMATLAB

The figure above displays the result of frequency in the bus power system model at Phasor Measurement Units and it has run for 0.02 seconds. The results came exactly as expected and there were errors or faults encountered during the simulation.

CURRENT DISCUSSION

In this part, the current was calculated using the results we got from Simulink Matlab’s bus model power system. Summary of citation of potential research related to power and supply, clearly indicating the increasing trend in recent years. Recent advancements in optimization

modelling provided ease to researchers to find optimal and sustainable solutions to the complex problems associated with power generation and supply scenarios. This research can be concluded that modelling and optimization are proven effective and useful tools for problem-solving in the power and supply sector and especially for policymakers to establish policies based on a detailed assessment of competing technologies and huge amounts of scenario analyses (Bazmi & Zahedi, 2011). There were many things related to software technology that can address the fluctuations of power variables (Frequency, current and voltage) that Synchrophasor technology addresses in the current study.

Kabeyi, 2019) (Haraldsson & Georgsson, 2018) (Singh et al., 2011).

CONCLUSION

The purpose of Phasor measurement is to produce a simplified representation of power system signals that accurately represent the actual system status. This research has introduced wide-area measurement technology integrated with Simulink MATLAB Software known as Synchrophasor technology. Through the 10-bus power system model in Simulink MATLAB, the voltage was measured, however, it didn't meet the expectation for three phases according to Kenya standards but it's quite normal. The results obtained during the calculation of the current turn out to be accurate according to the Kenya standard and show the possibility of the quality of electricity in the simulation.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Barasa Kabeyi, M. J. (2019). Geothermal Electricity Generation, Challenges, Opportunities and Recommendations. *International Journal of Advances in Scientific Research and Engineering*, 5(8), 53–95. <https://doi.org/10.31695/ijasre.2019.33408>
- [2]. Bazmi, A. A., & Zahedi, G. (2011). Sustainable energy systems: Role of optimization modelling techniques in power generation and supply - A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(8), 3480–3500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.05.003>
- [3]. Haraldsson, I. G., & Georgsson, L. S. (2018). UNU Geothermal Training Programme in Africa: Short Courses held in support of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the ICEIDA / NDF Geothermal Exploration Project. November.
- [4]. Karthick, T., Charles Raja, S., Jeslin Drusila Nesamalar, J., & Chandrasekaran, K. (2021). Design of IoT-based smart compact energy meter for monitoring and controlling the usage of energy and power quality issues with demand side management for a commercial building. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 26, 100454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2021.100454>
- [5]. Singh, B., Sharma, N., Tiwari, A., Verma, K., & Singh, S. (2011). Applications of phasor measurement units (PMUs) in electric power system networks incorporated with FACTS controllers. *International Journal of Engineering, Science and Technology*, 3(3), 64–82. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijest.v3i3.268423> (Barasa